

NOMAD: A Modular Infrastructure Ecosystem for FAIR Research Data Management

José A. Márquez^{1,*} , and the FAIRmat team.

¹ Department of Physics and CSMB, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin, Germany

² Leibniz-Institut für Kristallzüchtung (IKZ), Max-Born-Straße 2, 12489 Berlin, Germany

³ Technische Hochschule Wildau, Germany

⁴ Chair of Applied Physics, Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 91058 Erlangen, Germany

*Correspondence: José A. Márquez, jose.marquez@physik.hu-berlin.de

Abstract

Faced with critical global challenges related to energy, sustainability, and technological advancement, research fields like solid-state physics and materials science increasingly turn to data-driven approaches to accelerate discovery and ensure reproducibility. However, the digital transformation required for this shift is often hindered by fragmented and inadequate research data management practices, reliance on unstructured data, and limited data science and IT expertise.

In this contribution, we present the NOMAD ecosystem—a modular, open-source research data management (RDM) infrastructure designed to address these challenges by seamlessly integrating data acquisition, curation, publication, and analysis across a federated network of materials science laboratories. Developed within the FAIRmat consortium of Germany's National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI), NOMAD enables laboratories to embed FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data practices directly into their everyday research workflows.

FAIRmat supports a growing network of self-hosted NOMAD Oasis installations across diverse application scenarios, including high-throughput experimentation with combinatorial material libraries, specialized perovskite solar cell research, advanced multidimensional characterization techniques (e.g., electron microscopy, ARPES), and educational contexts involving open-source tools in academic curricula. This federated framework allows individual laboratories to retain full control over their data while ensuring interoperability within the broader NOMAD community, thus balancing local autonomy with the advantages of global data sharing and collaboration.

Keywords: NOMAD, Research Data Management, Materials Science, Solid-state Physics, FAIR Data.

Resources

- NOMAD. www.nomad-lab.eu, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366163>

Author contributions

José A. Márquez led the writing of the original draft. José A. Márquez, Lauri Himanen, Hampus Näsström, Sebastian Brückner, Sandor Brockhauser, Ahmed Mansour, and Markus Scheidgen contributed to conceptualization, data curation, software, supervision, investigation, and methodology. Martin Albrecht, Heiko Weber, Silvana Botti, Christoph T. Koch, and Claudia Draxl contributed to supervision, conceptualization, and funding acquisition. The FAIRmat team contributed to software development, methodology, and investigation.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

The authors are part of the NFDI consortium FAIRmat funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) – project 460197019.